
Research

Teacher's Perception towards the Effect of Cooperative Learning on Student's Academic Performance in Secondary Schools in Ethiopia: A Case of Guji Zone

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Abstract: The purpose of this study was to investigate the teacher's perception of the effect of cooperative learning on student's academic performance in secondary schools in Guji Zone. To achieve this purpose, an explanatory sequential mixed research design was employed. Questionnaires, interviews, and documents were used as instruments of data collection. Data was collected from seven secondary schools in the Guji Zone. A total of 200 teachers were involved in the study. Quantitative data were analyzed using frequency, percentage, mean, standard deviation, and Mann-Whitney test, while qualitative data were analyzed thematically. The findings of the study revealed that teachers' have a positive perception towards the effects of cooperation, and give less attention to its implementation in the classroom, but a significant difference was found between natural science and social science teachers. On the other hand, there was a consensus among respondents that cooperative learning is poorly implemented. Unwillingness of teachers and students, poor coordination, and large class sizes highly influenced the effectiveness of the program, while lack of principal attention moderately affected it. Based on the findings, teachers' poor implementation significantly affected the implementation of cooperative learning in secondary schools in the study area. Therefore, facilitating training, experience sharing, and continuous professional support programs were suggested to improve teachers' attitudes towards cooperative learning, whereas mobilizing a budget to build additional classrooms was suggested to solve the problem of large class sizes. The overall recommendation of the study is that awareness training should be provided for teachers and students on the role of cooperative group learning, and the government should give high emphasis and use ultimate efforts to shape the attitude of stakeholders towards cooperative learning programs. It was also recommended that further investigations be conducted, including other issues or tasks directly related to the program, like teacher training on cooperative learning and access to essential resources.

Keywords: cooperative learning, perception, student academic performance and teacher

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1. Introduction

This chapter is concerned with the introductory part of the thesis proposal. It includes the background of the study, the statement of the problem, the significance of the study, the objectives of the study, the delimitation of the study, the limitations of the study, the operational definition of terms, and the organization of the study.

1.1. Background of the Study

One of the most amazing and fruitful fields of educational theory, research, and practice is cooperative learning. Cooperative learning has grown in popularity over the last three decades as a method of instruction for all grade levels and subject areas (Tsai, 2005; Tseng, 2004). Numerous studies have demonstrated the value of cooperative learning for students (Ghaith, 2004; Law, 2011; Liao, 2009). For instance, according to Gillies (2008), cooperative learning instruction gives students the chance to interact with peers, improve communication among them, foster the growth of reading comprehension, and reduce anxiety. Others also claim that learning, in which a small group of students with a range of abilities and learning styles are included, is a successful teaching strategy, not only for learning what is taught but also for helping their teammates (Zain, 2009). This fosters a collaborative environment where students can work together until every member fully comprehends and completes a task (such as an assignment). Furthermore, it is believed that the practice of traditional teaching methods has changed due to cooperative learning and a student-centered approach, which has improved students' academic performance (Eslamian, 2012). Moreover, learning aims to actively engage students in the teaching and learning process and opens the door for students to actively engage in the teaching and learning process as opposed to simply absorbing information from the teacher (Isaacs, 2008).

Empirically, Adams (2015) conducted a study to look at how cooperative learning affected classroom instruction in the United States of America. The study proved that cooperative learning strategies were linked to a lot of benefits in the classroom. The study found that cooperative learning's beneficial interdependence and individual accountability features increased students' enthusiasm to acquire classroom material. Since the school system in the United States differs from that in Ethiopia, the study there provided a contextual research gap. Melnichuk (2017), conducted a study in England with the aim of determining the impact of cooperative learning on students' academic progress. The study found that students benefited from the cooperative learning strategy. It was discovered that cooperative learning helped the students develop their critical thinking skills and provided insights into how well they understood certain concepts. Compared to other traditional methods of learning, the opportunities offered by the cooperative learning approach inspire students to learn. The pupils favored the cooperative learning technique over all other learning approaches, it was discovered.

Furthermore, the study conducted by Njoroge (2013) on the impact of the cooperative learning strategy on students' academic performance found that "students' levels of academic motivation increased when cooperative learning strategies were used. This means that teachers must create methods or strategies that are appropriate for students with various backgrounds, learning styles, academic accomplishments, and interests. Therefore, it is asserted that cooperative learning systems can successfully solve this difficulty (Johnson & Johnson, 2004).

As a result, the traditional teacher-centered approach to teaching has come under fire for not including students in their own learning. The new methods are now promoted for better learning as a consequence of the impact of educational research and the creation of new educational technologies, and it is because of these circumstances that Ethiopia is forced to promote cooperative learning as one of the active learning methods used in classrooms (MoE, 2005). Alison (2010) asserts that traditional teaching and learning strategies were teacher-centered and frequently led to competitive classroom environments. Alternatively, cooperative learning techniques have been favored to help students improve their oral communication skills, social skills, and self-esteem; increase student retention; improve student satisfaction with their learning experience; and help students learn and achieve academically (Zain, 2009).

Since its introduction in Ethiopia, cooperative learning has been utilized to effectively implement learner-centered instruction to inspire students and enhance student interaction (MoE, 2012). With this approach, secondary school kids are performing better and developing their abilities. The students are divided into small groups to work and

learn together in the classroom (OEB, 2011). Despite this, there are various obstacles that restrict the use of cooperative learning techniques in secondary schools. Among the challenges of the implementation of cooperative learning practices, the perception of teachers may be one of the problems that hinder the practice of cooperative learning in secondary schools in Guji Zone. Hence, the focus of this study was to assess teachers' perceptions of the effect of cooperative learning on student's academic performance in secondary schools in the Guji zone.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

Cooperative learning comprises instructional methods in which teachers organize students into small groups, which then work together to help one another learn academic content" (Slavin, 2011). In all levels of education, students in cooperative situations achieved greater academic, social, and psychological benefits (Johnson & Johnson, 2005). Specifically, cooperative learning has been reported to improve students' academic achievement (Beck, 2008).

Cooperative learning implementation presents a challenge and has issues that need to be fixed: For instance, Anderson (2006) reported that most classroom time is spent in "teachers talk," with only 1% of the students' classroom time used for reasoning or expressing an attitude. The situation seems similar in Ethiopia's secondary schools. Despite the fact that the Ministry of Education stressed the significance of applying cooperative learning techniques in instruction at various levels to foster the development of students' problem-solving skills and abilities (MOE, 2002), Daniel (2007) illustrated in his study that the teaching-learning process has continued to be teacher-dominated in the majority of Ethiopian schools. The typical classroom setting involves forcing students to copy notes from the blackboard and listen to their teachers. Daniel makes the case that group learning, cooperative learning, problem solving, and learning by doing are limited in the study area.

So far, many studies have been conducted on factors affecting the implementation of cooperative learning. For instance, Keritha (2009) investigated students' attitudes about the cooperative learning technique and revealed that, due to fears such as possible low grades, students prefer to work on their own rather than within a group. On the other hand, a comparative study by John and Ling-ling in 2010 found that there is no connection between cooperative learning and foreign language fear. Besides, the study in Vietnam shows that in Vietnam, cooperative learning is now a popular and preferred mode of instruction. Since the school system in Vietnam differs from that in Ethiopia, the study there provided a contextual research gap. However, because teachers and students insisted that cooperative learning mainly served to aid in information retention rather than help students fully comprehend the literature they were studying, the purposes of this kind of instruction were frequently misunderstood.

In Ethiopia, Berhanu (2010) discovered that very few students actually participate in group work because they struggle with utilizing the target language, lack cooperation skills, and lack awareness. The other study conducted by Seid (2012) on the effect of cooperative learning on EFL students' reading comprehension achievement and grade 10 students' social skills showed that cooperative learning is effective for improving students' reading comprehension achievement. Tamirat (2011) carried out a study on the elements that prevent cooperative learning from being effectively implemented in the classroom. He discovered a negative association between teachers' and students' beliefs and their actual cooperative learning practices in the classroom and also mentioned that contextual, behavioral, and personal issues can make it difficult to practice cooperative learning effectively. It was concluded that cooperative learning has been rarely used in Ethiopian schools, despite the fact that it is prioritized by the government as the best approach. Those studies were narrow in their scope because they mainly focused on cooperative learning in a single subject and did not assess the effect of teacher perception on student performance. Besides, they did not explore teachers' perceptions of teachers' effects. Furthermore, they did not address factors associated with teachers' perceptions of the effect of cooperative learning. Moreover, they did not see differences across fields of study. The current study was distinct from the aforementioned studies that examined teachers' perceptions of the effect of cooperative learning on students' academic performance.

1.3. Research Questions

To achieve the central aim of the study, the following research questions were entertained in this study:

1. What was the perception of teachers towards the effect of cooperative learning on student's academic performance in secondary schools in Guji Zone?
2. What were the factors associated with the teachers' perceptions of the effect of cooperative learning?
3. Did the teacher's perceptions of the effect of cooperative learning vary across departments?

1.4. Objectives of the Study

1.4.1. General objective

The main objective of this study was to investigate the teacher's perception of the effect of cooperative learning on student's academic performance in secondary schools in the Guji zone.

1.4.1. Specific objectives

1. To identify the perception of teachers towards the effect of cooperative learning on student's academic performance in secondary schools in Guji Zone
2. To determine the factors associated with the teachers perceptions of the effect of cooperative learning in secondary schools in Guji Zone
3. To examine whether teachers's perceptions of the effect of cooperative learning vary across departments in secondary schools in Guji Zone

1.5. Significances of the Study

The findings of this study, which examine the teacher's perspective on the impact of cooperative learning on students' academic achievement, are anticipated to help teachers understand how their cooperative learning attitudes affect their students' academic performance. They also help teachers and school administrators understand how cooperative learning affects students' academic performance. Furthermore, the study's findings enhanced teachers' attitudes toward the cooperative learning method in terms of its applicability, administration, and enhancement of students' learning within the context of their schools. Moreover, findings are anticipated to shed light on the improvement of the teaching and learning environment. Finally, it was used as a source for future studies on cooperative learning.

1.6. Scope of the Study

This study was focused on investigating how teachers' perceptions of the effect of cooperative learning on student's academic performance in secondary schools in the Guji Zone and focused on independent variables (teacher background and teacher characteristics) and dependent variables (teacher's perceptions of the effect of cooperative learning). Geographically, in the Guji zone, there are 15 rural woredas and three administrative towns. From these, 4 (27%) out of 15 woredas were selected using cluster sampling, and three out of three administrative towns were selected using census sampling techniques. The study is limited to four rural woredas, namely Goro Dola, Wadera, Liben, and Adola Rede, and three town administrations, namely Nagelle, Adola Woyu, and Shakiso. It would be better if the study were conducted throughout the schools in the Guji zone. But due to the geographical set-up, infrastructure constraints, and time constraints, the researcher cannot conduct his research in all Guji Zone secondary schools. Therefore, the researcher was also delimiting his study to seven secondary schools. These seven secondary schools are: Nagele, Adola Woyu, Shakiso, Harakalo, Wadera, Bulbul, and Adola Rede. This was helping the researcher get relevant and representative information on the perceptions of teachers regarding the cooperative learning effect.

1.7 Limitations of the Study

The major limitation encountered by the researcher was that some respondents did not return the questionnaire on time. This is also another limitation of the study. Inadequacy of local research work regarding the topic being studied. To alleviate all of the above limitations, the researcher must have the patience to convince study participants by reviewing related literature from credible sources (websites) and getting institutional performance documents through repeated and continued visits to the school.

1.8. Operational Definition of Terms

Cooperative learning is a successful instructional approach where small teams of mixed-ability students (high, medium, and low academically achieving students) work together to take full advantage of their individual and group learning.

Perception: How do the teachers view cooperative learning practices in secondary schools in the Guji Zone?

Secondary School: It is a division of grade level that incorporates grades 9–12 that the study focuses on.

Student academic performance: The outcome of education is the extent to which students achieve their educational goals in the classroom.

Teachers: the selected secondary school members that participate directly in cooperative learning practice in the learning and teaching process.

1.9. Organization of the paper

This research consisted of five chapters. The first chapter deals with the background of the study, the statement of the study, the objective of the study, the significance of the study, the delimitation of the study, as well as the definition of terms. The second chapter is about the review of related literature, and the third chapter deals with research methodology. Chapter four contains data presentation, analysis, and interpretations. Provided in the last chapter are the summary, conclusion, and recommendation of the study. In addition to these, references and appendices of questionnaires, interviews, and other relevant documents are attached to the last part of the thesis.

2. Review of related literature

In this part, a brief review of the related literature to the major topic of the study was made. This was a theoretical review of cooperative learning, essential elements of cooperative learning, types of cooperative learning, and benefits of cooperative learning class activities in cooperative learning, factors affecting the implementation of cooperative learning and respondent's perception of cooperative learning are discussed.

2.1. Concepts of Cooperative learning

Cooperative learning was first included into educational programs in subject areas like social studies, science, and mathematics, according to a review of research and trends in the field. The researchers in the area of academic teaching and learning, however, focused on this strategy when these novel approaches showed promise in educational research. A teaching strategy known as cooperative learning involves having students of various backgrounds, talents, and abilities come together in small groups to work toward a common objective (Richards, 2001). Cooperative learning is group learning that is structured so that learning depends on the socially structured exchange of information between learners in groups. Each learner is responsible for their own learning in cooperative learning, and they are also encouraged to help others learn more. Cooperative learning has been given a lot of attention in studies that have been undertaken. Cooperative learning aims for learner-centered learning and makes claims that it will raise comprehension and reasoning levels, foster critical thinking, and improve long-term memory accuracy (Richards, 2001).

Additionally, Johnson (2000) propose that cooperative learning be incorporated into the mainstream of educational practice because it is a theoretically-based approach that has been shown to be significantly more effective than other non-cooperative instructional methods in enhancing student learning and improving social relations, and there are a variety of cooperative learning techniques that teachers can use. Johnson (2012) stated that cooperative learning is a

new paradigm of teaching that entails fostering the conditions for students to actively discover and construct their own knowledge, having them work together cooperatively to do so because learning is a social process rather than an individual one, developing each student's competencies and talents, and inspiring students through personal relationships.

According to Eslamian, (2012) the phrase refers to a novel strategy in educational practice that underpins student grouping involvement. In essence, this means that students form a sort of mutual aid group and collaborate to accomplish a common learning objective. Cooperative learning, according to Iijazi, (2012) is a type of learning when students work in groups to complete substantial cooperative tasks. Students who use this learning style are more likely to achieve higher levels of achievement, spend more time on tasks, form cross-ethnic friendships, feel more confident, develop lifelong interaction and communication skills, and master the mental habits (critical, creative, and self-regulated) required to be productive members of society. According to another academic, Knight (2009), cooperative learning is education that is mediated by the students rather than the teacher. High-quality group work depends on the social skills that are developed throughout group work-learning. Students participate in cooperative learning by working in groups to educate themselves on the material being studied (Stanine, 2000). Cooperative learning is an effective learner-focused teaching strategy wherein small teams made up of students of various academic achievement levels high, medium, and low work together to maximize both their individual and group learning (Johnson and Johnson, 2009).

2.2. Essential Elements of Cooperative Learning

Instructions for cooperative learning in the classroom must be accommodated for and numerous key components must be put into effect. Although it is considered that there are other cooperative learning techniques, Jonson and Johnson's (2009), suggests that grouping student's does not ensure that they will develop cooperative relationships. They recommended that the following five crucial components be properly constructed into the circumstance in order to foster cooperation and maximize the group's potential. These are positive interdependence, individual and personal accountability, face-to-face interaction, appropriate use of social skills, and group processing.

2.2.1. Positive Interdependence

The first component of cooperative learning is positive interdependence, which entails a cooperative lesson that is well-structured and in which students come to believe that they are sinking or swimming as a group. The teacher must establish a clear group or shared purpose, such as learning the assigned content, and make sure that all group members understand the information in order to make sure that students believe they "sink or swim together" and care about how much each other learns (Johnson and Jonson, 2000). Students who exhibit positive interdependence are more likely to: understand how their work benefits their group members and how their group members' work benefits them and collaborate in small groups to maximize everyone's learning by sharing resources to offer mutual support and encouragement.

2.2.2. Face-to-Face Interaction

Positive interdependence and promoter interaction have a linear relationship since they always result in interactions between the two. A situation that fosters interaction may be described as one in which people support and assist one another in their attempts to achieve, finish tasks, and produce certain results in order to meet the group's objectives. The role of face-to-face promoter interaction among individual students, which is fostered by positive relations, an adjusted psychology, and social competence of students, is paramount and indispensable, even though positive interdependence can take the lead in influencing the outcomes of the students and groups overall (Johnson, 2012). To mention, students can have the possibility to influence each other's efforts in order to achieve the group's goals; they can also act in trusting and trustworthy ways; being motivated to strive for mutual benefit; and maintaining a moderate level of arousal characterized by low anxiety and stress (Johnson, 2012).

However, there are cooperative learning activities or tasks that each student will complete independently. These activities and individual learning must come together to be shared for other participants. Consequently, it is essential to mix individual learning with group learning via exchanging experiences in order to achieve this interaction of students inside the group (Li, 2013). According to Liang (2002), there is a two-way relationship between face-to-face engagement and students' learning that resembles a cause-and-effect relationship. A cooperative learning environment in the classroom helps students develop both academically and socially. The group members' interaction

and supportive communication helped to achieve this. However, group interaction among students aims to complete academic assignments so that they can reach their ultimate shared objectives; this promotes face-to-face interaction among students in a way that improves their learning in various ways (Aschettino, 2000).

2.2.3. Individual Responsibility

Individual responsibility exists when classmates hold the student's accountable for making a fair contribution to the group's achievement. The group needs to be aware of who needs additional help, motivation, and support to do the task. Through cooperative learning, individual accountability is essential to ensuring the strength of every group member. To explain, the possibility that individual strength becomes solidified is higher since cooperative learning requires the involvement of all group members and allows each of them to get fresh insights from the other. Teachers must evaluate how much effort each student is putting forth for the group's work, give feedback to both groups and individual students, support groups in avoiding duplication of effort, and make sure that each member is accountable for the outcome in order to ensure that each student is individually accountable for doing his or her fair share of the work assigned to the group (Jonson and Johnson's, 2009).

2.2.4. Interpersonal and Small-Group Skills

Students may effectively manage their groups by applying their social skills in group discussions, which creates a foundation for developing such skills further. As part of their job responsibilities, teachers are supposed to teach their students these skills in the meantime. According to Johnson and Johnson (2009), students must: come to know and trust one another, communicate clearly and accurately, accept and support one another and resolve their agreement constructively in order to coordinate individual efforts to attain shared goals. In addition, they added, putting socially awkward people in a group and asking them to cooperate does not ensure that they will be able to do so successfully. Students should instead be taught social skills with the same intentionality and precision as academic capabilities. Students that possess leadership, decision-making, trust building, communication, and conflict-management abilities are better able to successfully handle both teamwork and individual projects (Koutselini, 2009).

2.2.5. Group Processing

Organizing group processing is the last step in the cooperative group discipline. Whether or not groups evaluate their performance has an impact on how successfully they can collaborate. According to Johnson & Johnson (2000), a process is a recognizable sequence of events that occur over time, and process goals are the events that are necessary to achieve result goals (Wang, 2007).

Group processing, in turn, is a component of cooperative learning that also includes accountability, interdependence, and interaction. It is an activity or process that includes duties like assessment and evaluation of the program's effectiveness in terms of the students' interdependence, face-to-face interaction, accountability and responsiveness for their own learning and that of others, as well as interpersonal and social skill learning and seating solution for any gaps (Kimamo, 2011). Typically, these cooperative learning components are the guidelines and/or requirements for cooperative learning classes as well as the resources needed for cooperative learning to be implemented successfully (Johnson and Johnson, 2009).

2.3. Teacher role in cooperative learning

2.3.1. Preparing lesson plan

The teacher should evaluate his/her learner in order to find out what exactly students are ready to know before teaching. Teachers must contemplate many important roles in cooperative learning to teach efficiently, that is specifying objectives, grouping students, explaining tasks, monitoring and group work, and evaluating achievement and cooperation (Frayadi, 2007). Teachers have their own important role in implementing cooperative learning, starting from preparing lessons up to applying that lesson plan in the classroom. As stated above, during preparing lesson plans teachers can take into consideration how to explain objectives, grouping students from different disabilities, cultural backgrounds, personalities, different learning differences and follow up each group activities.

Following lessons teachers can evaluate students' activities and they also allow the students" to present or summarize briefly what they discuss in their own given topics or lesson. So through these processes the teachers evaluate students" performance on the lesson. Teachers can use rules to evaluate students" performance. Students also can participate in the elevation of their learning from each other by using a peer fidelity checklist. Finally, teachers may

conclude the activities of each group by encouraging students to share answers and papers and summarize them in point of the lesson (Al .Refaee, 2006).

2.3.2. Arranging Classroom

The role of the teacher is forming students in small groups in a welcomed classroom by following a well organized and well palmed lesson plan. Cooperative leanings are effective when the group size is small. The larger group is difficult to arrange and organize for cooperative learning. In addition to preparing a well organized classroom for cooperative learning, teachers should have considered students' differences in standings of cultural background, disabilities, different abilities, language and gender difference while arranging students for cooperative learning. The other duties that teachers must consider during organizing a classroom is that each group should properly space to maintain eye- to eye contact, sharing tasks equally, and communicate without disturbing other groups (Bano, 2011).

Teachers should inform students about rules, procedures and exceptions from the students" to learn cooperatively. The teacher also tells the students to develop good relationships within their peers. Teachers should explain the three basic rules of cooperative learning, stay with your group, ask a question of your groups first before you ask your teacher for feedback and ideas and avoid criticizing people (Aschettino, 2000).

2.4. Educational Theories that Underlie Cooperative Learning

2.4.1. Original Theory of Cooperative Learning

There are two types of social interdependence: positive and negative. Positive interdependence exists when there is a positive correlation among individuals 'goal attainments; individuals perceive that they can attain their goals if and only if the other individuals with whom they are cooperatively linked attain their goals. Positive interdependence results in primitive interaction (i.e., individuals encouraging and facilitating each other's efforts to complete tasks in order to reach the group's goals). Negative interdependence exists when there is a negative correlation among individuals 'goal achievements; individuals perceive that they can obtain their goals if and only if the other individuals with whom they are competitively linked fail to obtain their goals. Negative interdependence results in oppositional interaction (i.e., individuals discouraging and obstructing each other's efforts to complete tasks in order to reach their goals). No interdependence exists when there is no correlation among individuals 'goal achievements; individuals perceive that the achievement of their goals is unrelated to the goal achievement of others. The basic premise of social interdependence theory is that how participants 'goals are structured determines the ways they interact and the interaction pattern determines the outcomes of the situation (Elsa, 2016).

2.4.2. Cognitive-Developmental Theory

The cognitive development perspective arose from the work of Piaget, (2004) and (Vygotsky, 2000). Based on Piaget and Vygotsky, theories of cognitive development and perspectives with those of their colleagues, Slavin R, (2011) stated that reciprocal interaction among children around suitable academic tasks creates growth in the knowledge of concepts and critical skills. This indicates that students' interactions in their group and participating together in every aspect of academic tasks help them to learn and are important to their cognitive developments.

Vygotsky's notion of the Zone of Proximal Development (ZPD) is meaningful to learning. Such learning happens through interaction with each other in the ZPD. Vygotsky defines the ZPD as: The distance between the actual developmental levels as determined by independent problem solving and the level of potential development as determined through problem solving under adult guidance or in collaboration with more capable peers (Vygotsky, 2000). Vygotsky stresses the importance of cooperative activities and argues that the development of children is promoted by cooperative activities. In his view, cooperative activities among children promote growth because children of the same age work in one another's ZPD and model behaviors, which is more effective than children working individually (SlavinE, 2011). Vygotsky, (2000) argues that functions are first formed in the collective in the form of relations among children and then become mental functions for the individual... Research shows that reflection is developed from argument. In the learning process, a crucial element is that it must stimulate inside growth that only happens when a child joins, in cooperation and interaction, with his or her peers (Vygotsky, 2000). In addition, knowledge is a societal product because cognitive processes are the outcomes of cultural and social interactions Vygotsky, (2000) and a cause of learning must be social interaction. To stress the importance of the role of social interaction Vygotsky,(2000) claims that individual learners first learn through individual to individual social interaction and then knowledge is individually internalized .Hence, social interaction needs to be encouraged in the

process of learning because if social interaction or group interaction does not exist, students may not reach any shared goals or achievement (Johnson & Johnson, 2008). The work of Piaget, (2004) supports the cognitive developmental perspective, and argues that knowledge, values, regulations, morals and systems of symbols may only be learned effectively through interaction among participants. Piaget's developmental theory emphasizes the involvement and participation of learners in the learning and thinking process. In the learning process, learners construct and reconstruct knowledge by themselves. Piaget, (2004) claims that an active discovery learning environment should be encouraged to provide students with opportunities for assimilation and accommodation. This means that learners will incorporate the new knowledge and then assimilate it to their existing knowledge. If the new knowledge is not consistent with the existing one, it needs accommodation and creates equilibrium Piaget, (2004). Accordingly, if equilibrium is maintained, and knowledge is constructed and reconstructed in relation to the existing knowledge of learners and learning environment, cognitive growth will be created (Piaget, 2004). In addition, Slavin (2011) stated that students cannot learn much from others, if there is no social interaction in learning. Both scholars stressed how much interaction and conversation help for students' learning, which can be applied more in cooperative learning.

2.4.3. Social Interdependence Theory

The origin of the theoretical approach to cooperation is social interdependence theory. Of the theories of cooperation, social interdependence theory is the most important in terms of research generated and practical applications. The initial formulation of social interdependence theory was published in (Eggen, 2001). Its roots, however, lie in the work of two earlier prominent psychologists. In the early 1900s, Kurt Koffka, one of the founders of Gestalt psychology proposed that groups were dynamic wholes in which the interdependence among members could vary. In the 1920s and 1930s, Koffka's proposal was extended by Kurt Lewin, who stated that: (a) the essence of a group is the interdependence among members (created by common goals) that resulted in the group being a dynamic whole so that a change in the state of any member or subgroup changes the state of all other members or subgroups; and (b) an intrinsic state of tension in group members motivates movement toward the accomplishment of the desired common goals. One of Levin's graduate students, Deutsch, (1962) extended Levin's notions to the relationship among the goals of two or more individuals. In doing so, he developed a theory of cooperation and competition. Deutsch, (1962) defined positive interdependence (i.e., cooperation) as existing when a situation is structured so that individuals' goal achievements are positively correlated; individuals perceive that they can reach their goals if, and only if, the others in the group also reach their goals. Thus, individuals seek outcomes that are beneficial to all those with whom they are cooperatively linked. He defined negative interdependence (i.e. competition) as existing when a situation is structured so that individuals' goal achievements are negatively correlated; each individual perceives that when one person achieves his or her goal, all others with whom he or she is competitively linked fail to achieve their goals. Thus, individuals seek an outcome that is personally beneficial but detrimental to all others in the situation. Later, Deutsch (1962) added individualistic efforts, which exist when a situation is structured so there is no correlation among participants' goal attainments. Each individual perceives that he or she can reach his or her goal regardless of whether other individuals attain or do not attain their goals (Deutsch, 1962). Thus, individuals seek an outcome that is personally beneficial without concern for the outcomes of others.

2.4.4. Social learning theory

Bandura, (1977) social learning theory states that neither inner forces nor environmental stimuli drive people as isolated influences. Behavior and complex learning must be explained in terms of a continuous reciprocal interaction of personal and environmental determinants that virtually all learning phenomena resulting from direct experience occurs on a clear basis by observing other people's behavior and its consequences for them'. Therefore, human behaviors are affected by observation and by direct experience. The social learning theory emphasizes that behaviors result from both the social interaction of people and their environments. Personal and environmental factors determine each other, and the influences are bi-directional. The social learning theory explains human behavior in terms of a continuous reciprocal interaction between cognitive, behavioral and environmental determinants. Interaction is viewed as a process of reciprocal determinism; behavior, mother personal factors, and environmental factors all operate as interlocking determinants of each other. Social interaction between learners and role models is required for social learning to occur. If there is no interaction, there is no learning. All these concepts justify the importance of student interaction within each other and their environment in learning, which is advocated by cooperative learning.

2.4.5. Motivational Theory

Motivational theories focus on reward that derives students to behave in a certain manner. A cooperative environment creates a context in which students want to help one another. This motivates students to do well for themselves and make sure the other members of the group are also doing so. Students striving to meet their goals are motivated to encourage and support their group members to bring forth their best effort. Cooperative goals create norms that affect students' achievement positively (Slavin, 2011). Consequently, academic achievement leads to social acceptance (Slavin, 2011). In the traditional classroom, the competitive and/or individualistic goals are not related positively. Actually, an individual's academic achievement is unrelated to the rest of the class or it is against it. Academic achievement is not seen positively by the other students. This discourages students from striving for academic excellence (Slavin, 2011).

2.5. Types of Cooperative Learning

There are three common types of cooperative learning. They are discussed hereby;

2.5.1 Formal Cooperative Learning

Formal cooperative learning is a form of cooperative learning in which a group of students collaborates for one class period to many weeks in order to accomplish common learning objectives and complete joint tasks and assignments (Johnson and Holubec, 2008). It is used to accomplish group goals in task work and is structured, assisted, and continuously observed by the instructor (e.g. completing a unit). This form of learning may be used for any project or course content, and groups can range in size from 2 to 6, with discussions lasting anything from a few minutes and a full class hour.

2.5.2 Informal Cooperative Learning

Informal cooperative learning groups are those that can change from lesson to lesson and are frequently transient. It entails setting up brief, ad hoc groups of students to collaborate on a shared learning objective for up to one class period (Johnson and Holubec, 2008). Informal cooperative learning, which usually involves groups of two, combines group learning with passive teaching by bringing attention to the content through small groups during the session or through discussion at the end of a lesson. Informal cooperative learning can be used during a lecture, demonstration, or film to direct students' attention to the material to be learned, create an environment that is conducive to learning, help set expectations for what will be covered in class, make sure that students are processing and practicing the material being taught, summarize what was learned and present it in the following session, and wrap up a lesson. Having concentrated talks before and after the class and including pair discussions within the lesson are two ways that teachers might employ informal cooperative learning to keep students more intellectually active (Mohammed, 2012).

2.5.3 Cooperative Base groups

Long-lasting, diverse cooperative learning groups with a steady membership are known as cooperative base groups (Johnson and Holubec, 2008). Members' main duties are to: make sure everyone is making good academic progress, hold one another accountable for trying to learn; and support, encourage, and help one another complete assignments. Periodically, teachers should impart the necessary social skills and ask the groups to evaluate their performance to ensure that the basic groups run smoothly. Cooperative base groups often include a variety of people, meet frequently, and stick around for the entire class, ideally for several years. The establishment of caring, supportive peer relationships in cooperative base groups, which in turn motivates and strengthens the students' commitment to the group's education while increasing self-esteem and self-worth, is effective for learning complex subject matter over the course of a semester. When using base group methods, students are held responsible for educating their peers if one of them missed a lesson. Both individual learning and social support can benefit from this (Aschettino, 2000).

2.6. Benefits of Cooperative Learning

It is clear how much cooperative learning is a multifaceted learning method from the concepts discussed in the definition and concept of cooperative learning section. Many more advantages arise when cooperative learning is successfully incorporated into classroom instruction, in addition to those already mentioned (Slavin, 2000). The use of cooperative learning in actual teaching and learning processes has the following advantages.

2.6.1. Academic Benefit

Researchers and education experts support the idea that cultivating a sense of "it is all in the same boat together," a fundamental cooperative learning concept, can optimize student learning and increase academic performance (Akhtar, 2012). Students gain academic and social benefits when the classroom is set up so that they can collaborate with one another on learning assignments. The concepts and materials being discussed in class can be discussed, debated, and clarified by students participating in cooperative learning groups. They can also assist one another in learning the foundational knowledge required for computational procedures. Similar to this, Slavin, (2000) hypothesized that the goal of cooperative work groups is to improve students' academic performance by giving them more opportunities for debate, peer learning, and mutual support.

2.6.2. Enhance Creativity

According to Johnson (2009), cooperative learning encourages creative thinking by boosting idea generation, idea quality, feelings of stimulation and enjoyment, and originality of expression in creative problem solving. It is not surprising that different viewpoints prompt group members to consider more options and that students are "triggered" by other people's ideas. A context for considering and appreciating other group members' ideas is also provided by the cooperative relationship, as opposed to disregarding (individualistic) or striving to come up with a superior one.

2.6.3. Psychological Benefits

Interpersonal relationships among students are facilitated by cooperative learning. Learners' self-esteem is increased by having the chance to discuss their ideas in smaller groups and receive helpful criticism. In a whole-class setting, students are required to answer a question in front of the entire group without having much time to consider their response. Due to the fact that group consensus rather than individual judgment is used to find solutions, cooperative learning fosters a secure and loving environment. Before presenting them to the class, mistakes are fixed in the group (Isaacs, 2008).

2.6.4. Social Benefit

Teaching social and interpersonal skills is one of cooperative learning's most beneficial applications. In cooperative learning teams, social skills are modeled by other group members in a safe, small-group setting (Johnson and Johnson, 2009). It is a setting where students may put new skills into practice. Students that participate in cooperative learning often develop a tolerance for different points of view, give others' opinions careful thought, and seek out more information to understand other people's ideas. Therefore, in order to achieve the necessary behaviors, social skills should be taught in a methodical manner, just like arithmetic, social studies, or any other topic.

2.6.5. Benefits for Teachers

Both teachers and students can be in charge of assessing the abilities and contributions of group members during cooperative learning. Teachers frequently gather and exchange information about how groups are working in relation to the academic and social parts of the lesson while students are participating in group activities (Isaacs, 2008). The groups are informed of this information both during and after the lesson. For teachers who are concerned about a learner's performance in a particular area, direct observation is a useful technique. In conclusion, it is possible to conclude that cooperative learning promotes both cognitive and affective growth based on the following benefits of the method as discussed by various academics (Isaacs, 2008). Moreover, cooperative learning benefits students to make higher achievement gains, higher level of self-esteem and greater motivation to learn. However, for the above explained benefits of cooperative learning to be realized, teachers need to be well acquainted with the various steps used to implement cooperative learning.

2.7. Class Activities in Cooperative Learning

At Kagan (2001) Publishing and Professional Development, Kagan and his colleagues have created a variety of cooperative learning exercises. Some of the cooperative learning exercises created by Kagan and his colleagues are listed here.

2.7.1. TanGram Learning

Each group member is given a different piece of content to study and then impart to the other members of his group as part of the Tangram concept. Tangram learning is designed to help all students improve their teamwork and cooperative learning skills. Additionally, it aids in the development of a depth of knowledge that would not be

possible if students attempted to master the entire course material on their own. This indicates that the Tan gram technique calls for an equal distribution of duties among cooperative learning teams, and that teams are in charge of understanding a particular area of knowledge and delivering that content to colleagues (Kagan, 2001).

2.7.2. Think pair-share

Usually, this approach is incorporated into lengthy classes and exercises. There are four steps in it. The teacher will first put a query or a problem to the class. Students are given time to reflect alone in the second step. Third, students are instructed to discuss their concepts with a partner, and fourth, the teacher asks a select few students to present their thoughts to the class as a whole. Rewards are not a primary component of this approach; instead, the focus is frequently on the planning stage of the thought process rather than finished work projects (Stahl, 2000).

2.7.3. Team Pair Solo (Kagan)

A cooperative learning strategy called team pair solo involves forming teams of students. They approach problems first as a team, then with a partner, and finally independently. It is intended to inspire students to take on and excel at challenges that are originally outside of their capabilities. It is founded on the straightforward idea of mediated learning. After finishing a problem, the team divides into pairs. After working on a similar problem in pairs, the students are divided into solo groups to work on the same problem alone. Utilizing this tactic gives you more confidence when tackling harder subjects. Additionally, it enables students to do more with assistance (mediation) than they otherwise could. In general, in spite of the differences among the different cooperative learning approaches, all cooperative learning strategies intended to have students believe a high degree of responsibility for their own learning rather than perceiving learning as imposed by others (Kagan, 2001).

2.7.4. Three-step Interview

One student interviews another about a predetermined topic during this structured group activity with students. When the allotted time has passed, students switch places as interviewer and interviewee. Students in each pair then combine to form groups of four and take turns introducing and discussing what their pair companions had to say. According to Olsen and Kagan (2001), this framework can be used to establish teams as well as for opinion questions, predicting, evaluating, sharing book reports, etc.

2.7.5. Numbered Heads Together

This format is practical for swiftly and entertainingly reviewing academic content. Each team's members are assigned numbers. Students help one another learn the content. A question and call number are posed by teachers. Only the students who have that number can respond and score points for their team, fostering both positive dependency and personal accountability. This could be done with just one student in the class replying (sequential form) or with all the numbers, like 3s, responding utilizing a strategy for every student to respond, like hand signals (Kagan, 2009).

2.7.6. Jigsaw

With this approach, students work in six-person teams on academic content that has been divided into portions (Slavin, 2000). Giving each student in a learning group access to information that represents just one section of a course encourages interdependence among the students. Following that, students are responsible for passing along the lesson to the other Jigsaw group members. Additionally, before attempting to teach the content to the students in their Jigsaw groups, the students from the various groups each of whom have the identical material to study meet in parallel groups to discuss and learn their respective portions of the lesson. Students work together in this manner.

2.7.7 Group Investigation (GI)

This broad organizational strategy for the classroom has the students working in small groups on cooperative projects, cooperative planning, and cooperative inquiry. Students create their own groups of two to six people using this technique. The groups then select subtopics from a unit that the entire class is studying, deconstruct those subtopics into individual assignments, and complete the tasks required to complete group reports. Then, for the purpose of sharing its findings with the entire class, each group creates a presentation or display (Slavin, 2000).

2.8. Factors Affecting the Implementation of Cooperative Learning

The effect of an event, circumstance, or experience reveals a person's inner world and attitude toward it. When studying language, the term "affect" relates to a person's viewpoint, emotions, sentiments, and mood. Among the

emotional components are motivation, self-esteem, self-confidence, and self-image (Zhu & Zhou, 2012). The implementation of cooperative learning may be impacted by a number of factors; hence, it primarily addresses individual, contextual, and other concerns.

2.8.1. Human Factors

Personal characteristics refer to a propensity or tendency to behave in a certain way. For example, extremely high or low self-esteem, authoritarianism (domination), anxiety, language skills, a lack of tolerance, a negative attitude toward cooperative learning, and a reluctance to speak up during cooperative learning activities can all have a significant negative impact on cooperative learning (Nunan, 2000). Because it is difficult to reject the ingrained patterns of conduct, humans are constantly resistant to ideas that go against their preconceived notions and practices.

2.8.1.1. Teacher

The adoption of pedagogical innovations may be impacted by the personality traits and beliefs of teachers. The adoption of educational innovations is reportedly influenced by aspects such as teachers' beliefs, attitudes, professional experiences, motivation, and comprehension of innovation, according to (Molalign, 2011). The quality of instruction in any classroom is dependent on the teacher's pedagogical viewpoint, independent of his or her skill and the teaching environment. A major issue with teachers learning about the cooperative learning approach, according to Hennessey (2013), is that the cooperative learning theories and terms that are presented to them in teacher training rarely take the teacher's context into account. The results have important ramifications for teachers since they must negotiate the different aspects influencing the implementation of cooperative learning, including the age and behavior of the student's, the size of the class, and the time. The development of abilities that allow future teachers to successfully use their theoretical knowledge in the classroom goes hand in hand with providing them with the knowledge and training essential in their field of specialization.

The academic and practical components of training, however, have not been adequately incorporated into Ethiopia's traditional teacher training program. The practice of teacher education, according to MoE(2003), is centered on the theoretical facets of subject knowledge. As a result, teacher educators must be well-trained and prepared to assume the duty if classroom learning is to be effective. Although more students would have studied and kept more of the content, cooperative learning was seen as time-consuming. This may be the case, particularly in the beginning when both the teacher and the student were unfamiliar with cooperative learning. In this regard, Palmer et al. (2003), as cited in Mohammed (2012), stated that teachers who are unfamiliar with cooperative learning may initially find it difficult to accept this style of learning because they may fear losing control of their classroom, be unsure of the technique used, or even believe it will take too much time.

2.8.1.2. Students

On the other hand, the implementation of cooperative learning is greatly influenced by students' awareness of how it is carried out and what is expected of them. According to Bethel (2011), the value of a student's experience is a transforming rather than passive acquisition of knowledge. They observe that students are likely to adopt a passive familiarity with the knowledge structure of the professors unless they explore the implications of the ideas in their own lives and decide to act now and believe in new ways. Attitude, motivation (affiliation and achievement), age, and prior language learning experience are frequent internal factors associated with psycho-social components that affect student's learning.

Each student's standard will be made up of all of these factors, and the sum of individual standards will, of course, make up the class standard. The inability to precisely execute the cooperative structure was the main source of the constraints. It wouldn't be unusual to find groups where one person handled the majority (or all) of the work, and the other students simply signed off as though they had learned it or had completed the task, if the teacher simply put the students into groups to learn and did not structure the positive interdependence and individual accountability. It may also be simple to have a "bossy" student who wouldn't let the others participate, or other issues with group dynamics that could arise from not establishing clear ground rules for behavior and carefully crafting the group dynamics (Kagan, 2009) as cited in Liang (2002). In addition, when each group member is made responsible for a unique part of the group's task, as in Jigsaw, group investigation, and related methods, there is danger that students may learn a great deal about the portion of the task they worked on themselves but not the rest of the content.

2.8.1.3. Principal

According to Boynton, (2007) management support is essential for changing teaching practices. In order to encourage his or her personnel to try out new ideas, the school principal's favorable opinion of an innovation achieved by practical support activities is essential (Holland, 2009) The principal's support for the innovation can be fulfilled through provision of resources, including time to participate, protection against intrusion, and recognition of accomplishment (Guskey, 2000), quoted in Shimeles (2012).

Cooperative learning should be encouraged at all costs by the school as a whole. This could entail spending money on conventional equipment or ordering books in sets for small groups to utilize. Simply keep in mind that school principals can be regarded as major figures in the school given that they are responsible for overseeing all activities that take place there. The school principal is often in charge of both the academic and administrative aspects of the institution. Furthermore, Bethel (2011) came to the conclusion that we need strong school administrators for any reform to be successful. Teachers are expected to get the required guidance and on-going professional support from school administrators. Teachers can only wholeheartedly support reforms if they understand the need for it and know that they will be supported.

2.8.2. Non-Human Factors

The normal process of cooperative learning may be impacted by contextual variables such as group size, group composition (heterogeneous groups are preferred), group cohesiveness (the degree to which members like each other), friendship, gender, age, time, discipline, staffroom environment, educational materials (Nunan, 2000).

2.8.2.1. Class Size

Different experiments and group projects should not be offered to large groups of students in a packed classroom. According to Bethel (2011), schools in many African countries have a sizable student body. It is challenging to give each student the attention they need and to meet their individual needs in order for them to participate fully in the learning process. Because of this, teachers employ lecturing to maintain control and impart knowledge to all students at once. What can be concluded from this is that the ideal class size for cooperative learning should have a sufficient number of students.

2.8.2.2. The Physical Environment

Many schools agreed that the physical environment including classroom layout, furniture placement, look, and other factors plays a significant role in fostering cooperative learning. A neat, well-kept classroom with the right materials can help create favorable expectations for a course. In Bethel (2011) stated that:

"Open classrooms are characterized by more active learning techniques involving frequent usage of group work, movement of learners between areas, the use of resource centers, independent work, etc... Additionally, the seating configurations will be mobile, with chairs that are not anchored to the floor.

2.8.2.3. Shortage of Instructional Materials

Instructional resources are essential because they give students the chance to learn independently and increase involvement through hands-on activities. In accordance with Brown (1994), instructional materials serve the following purposes: Encourage students to pay attention to the lesson, provide opportunities for learning by active participation and the immediate use of all senses and muscles, and assist students in fusing past knowledge with the prescribed material, which ranges from the abstract to the tangible. The low use of cooperative learning in language schools is generally attributed to a lack of teaching materials, such as a dearth of learning modules, maps.

2.8.2.4. The Organization of Curricular Materials

Cooperative learning implementation is greatly impacted by the way that curriculum materials (such as textbooks, teachers' guides, and other materials) are organized (syllabi, etc.). Most of the pre-packaged curriculum materials are overstuffed with data or content and have scant tasks and exercises. Regarding this concept, Hagose (2012) cited Lue (2000) who explained that teachers frequently skip the tasks and go on to the next unit because they are under pressure to finish the book and cover or present all of the information inside. Here, it is clear that this severely curtails students' ability to be creative on their own, which in turn makes it difficult to execute cooperative learning. The spoken group

lessons in the seventh-grade textbook, according to Wondwosen (2008) almost entirely meet the requirements of cooperative learning. However, there were several issues that restricted the use of cooperative learning, such as class size and the timeline for fixing the desks. In general, the discussion on the difficulties also imply that the instructor should pay attention to the potential barriers to group effectiveness such as lack of group maturity, motivation losses due to perceived inequality, lack of sufficient heterogeneity, uncritically giving one's dominant response and lack of teamwork skills (Wang 2007). Therefore, in order to achieve the benefit of cooperative learning, it is necessary to lessen the drawback by considering the basic components of cooperative learning while implementing it.

2.8.2.5. Lack of training for teachers'

Teachers are central to any success of implementation of cooperative learning. The quality of education depends on the quality of the teacher. Many teachers have poor training in special education to properly prepare lesson plans to teach students with disabilities cooperatively with their classmates. Lyser and Kirk, (2004), found that general education teachers generally use strategies and adaptation directed towards the class as a whole and incorporate only minor no modification based on student's needs. Here the main points of the school administrations need to provide training for teachers that give them the knowledge and skills needed to successfully implement cooperative learning in an inclusive classroom. Through different training teachers can learn how to consider the needs of students with disabilities with the rest of the students while he/she prepares daily lesson plans for teaching students with different disabilities. For implementing cooperative learning in an inclusive classroom, teachers who have traditionally worked in isolation will need to find new ways of collaborating and sharing their expertise (Areset.al, 1992).

Most of the time teachers do not teach the students how to coordinate their work with others and keep themselves in the learning. They simply give tasks and few students have done and have presents for the class. Teachers must have been among the group correcting miscommunication, helping students understand, and reinforcing good team work skills. Monitoring the groups carefully by observing interactions and encouraging appropriate learning and teamwork skills help the groups ensure mastery by every student keeping individual on their toes by asking them at random to explain their group work. Emmer and Gerwells, (2002), suggested that successful cooperative learning lesson characteristics: high individual accountability, higher teachers' monitoring and use of manipulative, task interdependence at a high amount of feedback. It is important that teachers' set guidelines from the outset of cooperative learning.

2.9. Perception towards cooperative learning

Perception is the procedure through which organisms interpret and organize sensation to form a meaningful experience of the outside world, according to Lindsey & Norman (2000), as stated in (Mekonenn., 2011). Contrarily, perception refers to a person's overall perception of reality and is often the result of additional sensory processing. Many academics believe that perception is a necessary component of live practice, and they assert that without practice, perception would be useless and unguided. Perception and practice are the "two sides of the coin" that are necessary for effective animated practice.

2.9.1. Students' Perception of Cooperative Learning

In the process of learning a language, attitude is crucial. The way a student feels about the language they are learning will affect them outside of the classroom. According to the research of Burden (2004), which Hagose (2012) mentioned, having a positive outlook on life can inspire students to attain their academic objectives. If a student is motivated to learn a foreign language during the English learning process, this positive outlook will benefit his or her academic performance. Cooperative learning in the classroom and how students perceive it has been the subject of numerous studies. The results of a study on students' attitudes and views of the usefulness of mobile learning, conducted by Fahad(2009), show that many students value cooperative learning as a way to increase their retention of the teaching and learning process.

Additionally, in his lesson, the student's executed cooperative learning exercises well. Fahad, (2009) cites Caroline et al (2009) research on "low ability students' impressions of cooperative learning." And they claim that despite there being challenging organizational and instructional issues that must be resolved before students can fully benefit from cooperative learning programs, low ability students still saw it as a potent teaching or learning method to help them become more skilled at interacting with others. With the exception of a few instances during the actual implementation of cooperative learning, students were successful. In the survey, the vast majority of students

reported having a sense of belonging that helped them communicate effectively with both the instructor and other students. While the instructor's position was largely passive, the students recognized their responsibility as active learners. The idea of cooperative learning is also accepted by the students as a way to improve academic performance, self-esteem, attitudes toward learning, and the growth of constructive relationships, among other things. Additionally, in the study, students expressed a high preference for working together over competing with one another or acting independently and they were successful in putting cooperative learning into practice.

2.9.2. Teachers’ Perception of Cooperative Learning

Associated with how teachers view cooperative learning, Thanh-Pham (2010) has studied how teachers might integrate educational innovation, specifically in the context of establishing cooperative learning. According to the study, there is a significant issue with the implementation of cooperative learning among many Vietnamese teachers. Their negative perspective of cooperative learning was the cause of this. According to the study, many cooperative learning ideas go directly counter to how Vietnamese teachers have traditionally viewed the relationship between teaching and learning. Cooperative learning in the classroom has also been evaluated (Mekonenn, 2011). Based on pre- and post-course observations, the study found a substantial treatment impact for four of the five fundamental principles thought to be necessary for a cooperative educational activity, with the exception of individual accountability. The researcher also rated the advantages of cooperative learning over competitive or individualistic learning quite favourably. Additionally, a brief study on the attitudes of two Thai teachers regarding cooperative learning was undertaken by (Tippawan, 2008). Based on teachers' prior classroom experience, the study was carried out. According to the survey, new teachers lack confidence in their ability to successfully integrate cooperative learning. However, the instructor with more classroom experience did a fantastic job of promoting cooperative learning. His conclusion thus made it very evident that experience alone has an effect on how cooperative learning is implemented. Despite this, both educators agree that using cooperative learning will improve students' academic performance and interaction. The study by Berhanu (2000) examines the application of cooperative learning in group projects. According to his findings, cooperative language learning is not frequently done, and many of the components of cooperative learning courses are not regularly used. He also comes to the conclusion that there is a lack of cooperation between many teachers and student’s when it comes to learning English. There is little data on how teachers and students view cooperative learning as a useful teaching strategy (Hennessey, 2013). In addition to the aforementioned research findings, numerous project works on teachers' perceptions of cooperative learning have previously been carried out abroad. Almost all research works reported many teachers committed to using cooperative learning and they felt positive about the role of the method on the pupil in their classes.

2.10. Conceptual Framework

A conceptual framework for determining the effect of using cooperative learning approaches on students’ academic achievement was independent variables and dependent variables. The independent variables (teacher background and teacher characteristics) and dependent variable was teacher’s perception towards effect of cooperative learning represented diagrammatically below.

Figure 1: Cooperative Learning Approach and Student’s Academic performance

3. Research methodology

In this section, research method, design of the study, participants of the study, instruments used, and procedures of the study, validity and reliability of data collection instruments and methods of data analysis are presented.

3.1. Research design

Research design is needed because it facilitates various research operations, thereby making research as efficient as possible, yielding maximal information with minimal expenditure of effort, time and money (Kothari, 2004). Explanatory sequential mixed design was employed in this study. It involves a two-phase project in which the researcher collects quantitative data in the first phase, analyzes the results, and then uses the results to plan (or build on to) the second, qualitative phase. The quantitative results typically inform the types of participants to be purposefully selected for the qualitative phase and the types of questions that were asked of the participants (Creswell, 2012). It helps research design as it helps to gather data at a particular point in time with the intention of describing the nature of existing conditions or practice. This design helps as a fact finding method with adequate and accurate interpretation of the findings. Moreover, this research design enables the researchers to come up with valid conclusions of the study. Selection of a particular research design is based on the philosophical assumption of the researcher, strategies of inquiry and specific research methods (Creswell, 2003). As this design is used to explain the current situations by describing what exists now and a mixed approach was employed concurrently to address the three basic research questions which underlined to investigate the teacher's perception towards the effect of cooperative learning on student's academic performance in Secondary Schools in Guji zone.

3.2. Research Method

The study employed a mixed method with the purpose of collecting and analyzing both quantitative and qualitative data. There were some rationales to use mixed methods approaches for this study. First, using such a method was advantageous to examine the same phenomenon from multiple perspectives (Cohen et al, 2007). Second, a mixed approach is important to build upon the strength that exists between quantitative and qualitative methods in order to understand a given phenomenon than is possible using either quantitative or qualitative methods alone (Jick, 2008).

3.3. Population, Sample, and Sampling Techniques

The target population of the study was teachers in secondary schools. In this study, the student researcher believes they were the right sources of information on the issue under investigation. In the Guji zone, there are 15 rural Woredas and three administrative towns. From these three administrative towns and four rural Woredas were selected using stratified sampling techniques, because it requires that the population be divided into strata before sampling takes place within each stratum. From these, 4 (27%) out of 15 woredas and 3(100%) administrative towns were included as a sample for its manageability. Thus, for this study, from rural Woredas Goro Dola, Wadera, Liben and Adola Rede were selected using simple random sampling technique all administrative towns namely (Negele, Adola woyu, and Shakiso) were included in the study. Therefore, one school was selected from each administrative town (Nagele, AdolaWoyu, and Shakiso) and rural woreda (Harakalo, Wadera, Bulbul and Adola Rede) were selected using simple random sampling techniques. Staff within a sample school out of 510 target population of teacher 224(44%) teachers were selected using simple random sampling techniques and seven senior teachers were selected using purposive sampling technique. Those teachers were considered as a sample frame for the study. Particularly, the teachers who are working in seven secondary schools whose total number are 510. So that representative sample teachers were chosen from seven schools' teachers.

Therefore, the sample size is calculated using simplified formula (Israel, 1992) as follow

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

Where, n= the total sample size

N= the total population of sampled colleges

e =the error of 5 percentage point (0.05)

$$\begin{aligned}
 n &= \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2} \\
 &= \frac{510}{1 + 510(0.05)^2} \\
 &= \frac{510}{1 + 510(0.0025)} \\
 &= \frac{510}{1 + 1.275} \\
 &= \frac{510}{2.275}
 \end{aligned}$$

= 224 (44%) of teachers were selected

Finally, based on the schools teachers’ size, the total sample size was proportionally allocated for the seven secondary school teachers.

Table 1: Population, Samples and Sampling Techniques

Category	Population	Sample	Sample (%)	Sampling techniques
Woreda	15	4	27%	Stratified random sampling
Administrative Town	3	3	100%	
School	52	7	13.5%	Simple random sampling techniques
Teachers	510	224	44%	Simple random sampling techniques

Source: Researcher survey, 2022/23

3.4. Sources of Data

Data about cooperative learning could be collected from the sources that can be involved directly or indirectly. In this study, the primary sources of data were teachers. The reason was because they were directly participating in implementation of cooperative learning practices in secondary school and they were given responses easily on the perception of teachers.

3.5. Instrument

The main data gathering tools used in this study was questionnaires and interviews

3.5.1. Questionnaire

According to Kothari (2001), questionnaires are frequently used in educational research to learn more about specific conditions and procedures as well as to elicit opinions and attitudes from both individuals and groups. To gather information from teachers and school leaders the questionnaires were prepared closed-ended questions in order to gather accurate data. There won't be many open-ended questions because this tool encourages in-depth research, but when there are, they are justified by the need for the respondent to express themselves freely (Best, 2003). The questionnaire was administered to the 224 secondary school teachers to procure information on the role played in establishing and enhancing the effect of cooperative learning in student academic performance. The questionnaire obtained through 5 point Likert Scale (strongly agree=5, Agree =4, Undecided =3, Disagree =2 and strongly disagree=1) questionnaires were organized and tabulated around the subtopics related to the research questions. The questionnaires have two categories: the respondent demographic characteristics and items relevant to the issue under investigation.

3.5.2. Interview

In addition to the questionnaire, the interview was the other instrument used to collect data for the study. The interview was undertaken to get views and opinions about the perception of teachers towards cooperative learning practice. Semi-structured interview was used to get more information from 7 senior teachers drawn from the respondents. Researchers chose senior teachers because with the assumption that they could be more familiar with cooperative learning issues and they know the teacher's perspective towards cooperative learning better than novice teachers. This was suitable for the researcher to elicit the accurate response. The main purpose of the interview was to substantiate the result obtained from the questionnaire, so as to obtain a great depth of information. Interviews allowed probing and asking for clarification of questions, interview questions were prepared based on the research questions in English for supervisors. The interview was conducted through face to face discussion. The interview was conducted in school using the time table of the researcher. The interview was recorded to get full information from the respondents.

3.6. Validity and Reliability Checks

First of all questionnaire and interview guide were checked for its face, content and construct validity through peer and advisor reviews. Then, the internal consistency or reliability of the instrument was tested in the first week of May, 2023 by pilot test on Bore secondary school, which was found in Guji Zone. The questionnaire was distributed for 30 teachers who teach from grade 9-12. From 30 teachers, 28 teachers responded while 2 of them didn't turn in the questionnaire paper.

After the dispatched questionnaires were returned, necessary modification on items and complete removal and replacement of unclear questions were done. Additionally the reliability of the instrument was measured by using Cronbach alpha test. A reliability test was performed to check the consistency and accuracy of the measurement scales. The remaining 24 items reliability was calculated by SPSS version 20, and Cronbach's Alpha was 0.881, indicating questions in each construct are measuring a similar concept. As suggested by Cronbach (as cited by Tech-Hong & Waheed, 2011), the reliability coefficients between 0.70–0.90 are generally found to be internally consistent. The content validity of the instrument was checked by the advisor and co-advisor.

Table 2: Reliability test results with Cronbach's alpha

Basic Questions	Number of items	Cronbach's alpha
What was the perception of teachers towards the effect of cooperative learning on student's academic performance in secondary schools in Guji zone?	8	0.873
What were the factors associated with the teachers' perceptions towards the effect of cooperative learning?	10	0.88
Did the teacher's perceptions towards the effect of cooperative learning vary across departments?	6	0.891
Average reliability	24	0.881

3.7. Procedures of Data Collection

After having adequate reading on available literature on the effect of cooperative learning on students' academic performance approach and related issues, the tools for data collection were developed. The researcher was establishing the basic questions of the study with the design adaptation and developments of the questionnaire were based. The instruments were given to the advisor and co-advisor in order to comment on the extent to which the items

were appropriate in securing relevant information to the research. Then after, some amendments were made based on the feedback obtained from the advisor. The questionnaires were prepared in English for teachers. Participants' consent were given priority and they were told about the purpose of the study and the consequences of their honest responses for the reliability of findings, then the researchers himself distributed and collected by making himself available for clarifying unclear questions. The modified questionnaires were distributed to 224 teachers. Finally, the data collected from different sources were analyzed accordingly.

3.8. Method of Data Analysis

According to Neuman (2003), a researcher presents the tables in a quantitative data analysis to provide readers a brief overview of the data. The reader can see the proof gathered by the researcher in the tables, and can determine for them what this study is about. On the basis of this, the researcher used frequency tables to illustrate the general reaction of educators. The collected data was interpreted and analyzed separately. In this study, both qualitative and quantitative data analysis methods were used since both methods were used to collect data. The quantitative data gathered through a close-ended questionnaire was presented and analyzed using Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version 21. To arrive at the intended analysis, several sets of statistical tools were performed. These were mean, standard deviation and Man-Whitney U test were used for analysis. Percentage and frequency count was used to analyze the demographic data of participants. Mean and standard deviation was used for the first and second objective (perception of teachers towards the effect of cooperative learning on student's academic performance and factors associated to the teacher's perceptions towards effect of cooperative learning). Man-Whitney was used to identify the difference among departments group two independent respondent groups existed and the researcher's intention was to confirm the existing opinion (response) difference between the two independent groups N.S. teachers include (natural sciences and mathematics) departments and S.S. teachers include (social sciences and language departments) Man-Whitney test was computed (Cohen et al, 2007). The analysis of qualitative data was treated by organizing and sorting the data at different stages of the analysis and explaining in line with quantitative data. Qualitative data analysis involves verbal argumentations and explanations. Since analysis of qualitative data occurs simultaneously with data collection, the first step in data analysis was to manage the data so that it was studied. Therefore, data collected through open-ended questionnaires, and interviews were analyzed qualitatively by narration to complement the main data. Finally the data was analyzed and discussed to reach certain findings and which in turn to give conclusion & possible recommendation.

3.9. Ethical Considerations

Ethical permission was obtained from the respective Bule Hora University; a formal letter was submitted to all concerned bodies to obtain their co-operation. The researcher was asked permission from the Woreda Education Office and secondary schools to collect data from teachers. Moreover, all participants of the study were informed about the purpose and benefit of the study just to secure their consent. Furthermore, all the participants were resumed confidentiality by explaining to them that their names and other clues of the status were not documented in the study. Any data and information given by them was kept confidential so that no one had opportunity to relate response to any one of them, and the data and information they provided was not used for anything other than this study.

4. Presentation, analysis and interpretation of data

This section of the study presents the presentation, analysis and interpretation of the data collected from respondents. Both qualitative and quantitative data that were collected from different participants via different instruments were presented and analyzed thoroughly. The chapter contains two parts. The first part is about the background of respondents and the second part deals with the presentation, and analysis of data related to research objectives.

The questionnaires were distributed to 224 secondary school teachers. But properly filled and returned questionnaires were 200 (90.9%), and all 7 teachers volunteered for the interview. The 20(9.1%) questionnaires were lost or not included in the analyses for containing incomplete information. Thus, the non-returned rate had no significant effect on the results.

4.1. Characteristics of the Respondents

Under this subtopic the sex, age, educational level field of specialization, work experiences, and current position of the respondents were presented.

Table 3: Characteristics of the Respondents

Characteristics	Category of Variable	N=200	
		N	%
1 Sex	Male	174	87
	Female	26	13
2 Age:	≤ 25 years	3	1.5
	26-30 years	8	4
	31-35 years	105	52.5
	36-40 years	60	30
	Above 40	24	12
3 Educational Level	Certificate level	-	-
	College diploma	-	-
	BA/BSc/ Bed	167	83.5
	MA/MSc	33	16.5
4 Field of study	EdPM	14	7
	Natural Science in teaching	73	36.5
	Social Science in teaching	73	36.5
	Language in teaching	20	10
	Mathematics in teaching	20	10
5 Years of service	under 5 years	3	1.5
	6-10	70	35
	11-15	91	45.5
	16-20	30	15
	Above 21	6	3

Table 3 shows the total composition of the sample of schools and the frequency of respondents that were selected from each school. Total 200 (89.3%) teachers and 7(100%) of senior teachers were selected as respondents from 7 secondary schools. From the total respondents that participated in answering the question and interview of the study 29 (14%) are females and 178(86%) are males. This value indicates that the number of female teachers and senior teachers in the school is not proportional.

Table 3 also indicates the age of respondents and qualification. 3(1.5%) of the teachers respondents had an age of 25 and below years, 8 (4%) teacher respondents had an age of 26-30 years, 165 (82.5%) teachers have an age of 31-40 years, the remaining 24 (12%) of teacher respondents and 7 (100%) of seiner teacher respondents had an age of above 40 years respectively. The age of the respondent was suitable for the study to give the response easily.

On the other hand, this table shows the qualifications of the respondents. 167 (83.5%) of teacher respondents and 2(28.2%) of seiner teacher respondents were qualified by BSc/Bed/BA respectively, 33(16.5%) of teacher respondents and 5(71.4%) of seiner teacher respondents had Master degree holders respectively. The qualification of the respondents was good for the study to read and understand the questionnaire to give a genuine response.

Under item 4 of the above table 3, the teachers, and seiner teachers were asked to indicate their areas of specialization. Accordingly, 73(36.5%) of teacher respondents and 2(28.6%) of seiner teacher respondents were natural science and social science field graduates respectively. 20(10%) of teacher respondents and 1(14.3%)of seiner teacher respondents were graduates of language and mathematics respectively, and the remaining 14(7%) and 1(14.3%) of teacher and seiner teacher were graduates of EdPM respectively. So, it is important for the researcher in order to gather relevant data collected for the profession of the field in teaching.

The same table 3, also indicates the work experience and current position of respondents. 3(1.5%) of teacher respondents had an services of 5 and under 5 years, 70 (35%) of teacher respondents had an experience of 6-10 years,

121 (60.5%) and 2(28.6%) of teacher and seiner teacher respondents had an experience of 11-20 years respectively and 6 (3%) and 5 (71.4%) of teacher and seiner teacher respondents had an experience of above 20 years respectively. The work of experience of the respondents was used for the study to get relevant responses from the respondent by comparing the activities done in the school yearly.

4.2. Perception of teachers towards the effect of cooperative learning on student’s academic performance

The researcher designed perception items to be filled by teachers from items 1-8. The intention of the items was to assess teachers’ perception towards cooperative learning on student’s academic performance. The results of teachers’ responses to the attitude items were calculated and presented in Table below.

Table 4: Rating of teachers ‘perception

No	Items	N	Mean	STD
1	I have more awareness to practice cooperative learning to do it well	200	3.1	1.42
2	I have get more training in practice of cooperative learning more and I do it well	200	2.8	1.25
3	Teachers trust on the value of cooperative learning for academic achievement	200	3.45	1.04
4	I think cooperative learning is advantageous for students’ learning	200	4.2	0.93
5	Cooperative learning affects students’ academic achievement positively	200	3.53	1.00
6	Cooperative learning facilitates students to use higher level thinking strategies	200	2.7	1.34
7	I think teachers should know the essential elements of cooperative learning for successful learning	200	3.41	0.94
8	I think cooperative learning makes students responsible for their learning	200	3.2	1.34

In item 1 of table 4, the teacher respondents were asked to rate awareness of teachers to practice cooperative learning is well developed or not. Consequently, teachers were undecided (M=3.1, SD=1.42) with the idea. Tamirat (2011) pointed out that teachers were not equipped with how to implement cooperative learning; they have lack of knowledge to implement it since they didn’t take any course in undergraduate program about cooperative learning. From the results of the respondents, it was concluded that teacher awareness of teachers is not developed well to practice Cooperative learning actively.

Concerning item 2, the mean scores of teachers (M=2.8, SD=1.25)were undecided with the idea that I have to get more training in practice of cooperative learning more and I do it well. Then, from the result it was concluded that there is a training gap to participate well in cooperative learning practices in sample secondary schools.

Regarding item 3, Teachers trust on the value of cooperative learning for academic achievement, teachers agreed with the (3.45, STD= 1.04) on cooperative learning for academic achievement of students. This indicates teachers agree on the value of cooperative learning to encourage students to develop face- to- face communication skills as well as to make the activities, assignments, project works, and/or worksheets more simple or easy to complete. Active teaching learning pedagogy enhances learners to make maximum interaction with classmates (Derebsa, 2006).

Concerning item 4, the mean scores of teachers (M=4.2, STD=0.93)fall under agreement with the idea that I think cooperative learning is advantageous for students’ learning. From this, it is possible to say that cooperative learning makes students responsible for their learning.

With regards to item 5, of above table 4, the mean scores result of teachers respondents were (M=3.53, SD=1.00) fall under agreement with the idea that cooperative learning affects students’ academic achievement positively.

Regarding item 6,Cooperative learning facilitates students to use higher level thinking strategies. Teachers rated their response undecided with mean values of (M=2.7, SD=1.34).

Regarding table 4 of item 7, respondents were asked whether the teachers should know the essential elements of cooperative learning for successful learning or not; consequently, teachers were agreed with mean value of (M=3.41, SD=0.94). This confirms that teachers know the essential elements of cooperative learning for successful learning in sampled schools but not implemented effectively.

Regarding to the above ideas of the interviewee of seiner teachers participants states their views as follows

Actually proper implementation of cooperative learning in the actual teaching learning process is not a simple task; especially in a situation, where there is no adequate supervision and training. Therefore, in our school, particularly in my school cooperative learning implementation can be evaluated as low and as to me, this low practice of cooperative learning might not be caused due to attitudinal problem of teachers towards cooperative learning it rather might be due to teachers' lack of knowledge on how to meaningfully implement it. Accordingly, the interview result found from the above interviewees can be summarized that the status of the implementation of cooperative learning was low and the reason for this situation was lack of teachers' knowledge on cooperative learning rather than their attitudinal problems.

In general, based on the data collected from the different sources via different instruments regarding teachers' perception towards cooperative learning, it is possible to say that teachers have positive perception on cooperative learning. Similar to this finding Berhanu (2000) found that though teachers did not effectively practice cooperative learning, they had a favorable perception towards cooperative learning.

With regards to item 8, of the above table the mean scores result of teachers respondents were (M=3.2, SD=1.34) fall under moderately with the idea that cooperative learning makes students responsible for their learning.

4.3. Factors associated to teacher's perceptions towards effect of cooperative learning

As described by Muhamed, (2012), the implementation of cooperative learning encounters various challenges. As a study on teacher's perceptions towards the effect of cooperative learning in Guji Zone there are serious problems such as the motivation of students to work in groups, time shortage, as well as failure of instructors to give relevant feedback on time (Muhamed, 2012). In relation to this, the researcher has adopted the following items to assess the factors that may hinder implementation and effectiveness of cooperative learning in selected study areas.

Table 5: Rating of factors associated to teacher's perceptions

No	Items	N	Mean	STD
1	Low understanding of teachers about cooperative learning	200	3.35	1.43
2	Unwillingness of students to work in cooperative learning group	200	3.63	0.55
3	Unwillingness of teachers to implement cooperative learning	200	3.45	1.1
4	Very large group size and uncomfortable seating arrangement of students	200	3.72	0.48
5	Poor training of teachers to implement and coordinate	200	3.42	1.03
6	The existence of large number of students in one class	200	3.47	0.89
7	Domination of some students over the others during group work	200	3.41	0.98
8	Lack of student confidence to express their views	200	3.44	0.94
9	Poor educational background of students	200	3.42	1.00
10	Teachers inability to provide clear procedures on how to perform the activity	200	3.40	0.99

Analysis shows that item 1 about low understanding of teachers as a factor for implementation of cooperative learning teacher respondents (M = 3.35 and STD= 1.43) show that they have moderate agreement with that understanding of teachers as a moderate factor that hinder the implementation and effectiveness of cooperative learning.

Item 2 about unwillingness of students to work in cooperative learning group teacher respondents strongly agree as it is a factor which hinder the implementation of cooperative learning with the mean score of (M=3.63, STD=0.55) this show that unwillingness of students to work uncooperative learning group is a powerful factor which limit its effectiveness and implementation.

Similarly on item 3 about unwillingness of teachers to implement cooperative learning teacher respondent score with mean (M =3.45, STD=1.1) this indicates that it has a high impact on implementation and effectiveness on cooperative learning.

Regarding item 4, about very large group size and uncomfortable seating arrangement of students with the mean value of teacher respondents (M= 3.72, STD= 0.48) this shows that very large group size and uncomfortable seating arrangement of students have a high impact on implementation of cooperative learning.

Concerning item 5 in the above table about Poor training of teachers to implement and coordinate teachers, respondents agreed with the mean score of (M= 3.42, STD=1.03). This shows that lack (poor) training of teachers about cooperative learning is affecting the implementation of cooperative learning.

Regarding the above items 1-5, ideas of the interviewee participant member states their views as follows.

"The results from interviews held with senior teachers and document analysis also show that cooperative learning of active pedagogical approaches to ensure quality of education we are facing a lot of challenges. Among those factors, the attitude related problems and lack of interest of teachers and students to accept or trust its implementation the most challenging. Our class size is also challenging to form groups. However, as principle the number of group members recommended are 5-7 but practically one group may have up to nine members depending on the class size. As a solution, I expect that it is important to have detailed discussion with teachers and students to have common agreement especially on its value and implementation strategies. It is also important to reward those who are involved in the program more effectively and motivate others.

Three of senior teachers also described the factors as, "Reluctance and/ or unwillingness of teachers to facilitate students, to support the students" discussion through worksheets or by giving organized tasks. In addition to this, the presence of a large number of students in a class is another problem. Lack of understanding about its implementation strategies may hinder its effectiveness. However, it is not new for teachers" further training will enhance both teachers and students. Nevertheless, what I understand about the factors is not related to understanding the problem/lack of knowledge, rather I feel that it is more related to attitude problems or lack of trust and unwillingness of both teachers and students. Therefore, as a solution to improve its implementation and effectiveness, I think it is important to make more discussions to convince teachers and students and have common agreement as well as having a good reward culture specifically based on the performance of tasks directly related to cooperative learning."

In the case of item 6 of above table 5, the respondents were requested to decide whether the existence of a large number of students in one class or not. Consequently, teachers agreed with the (M=3.47, STD=0.89) on the issue. This indicates that the existence of a large number of students in one class and uncomfortable seating arrangement of students were extremely affecting cooperative learning.

Another interviewee also expressed

"Lesson delivery through different methods and uncomfortable sitting arrangement of students due to their large numbers are the major factors affecting cooperative learning".

Yet, Aschalew (2013) found out that large class size is a serious problem affecting the implementation of active learning. With regards to item 7 and 8, the mean scores result of teachers 'respondents were (M=3.41, SD=0.98) and (M=3.44, SD=0.94) respectively. This indicated that domination of some students over the others during group work were moderately affecting cooperative learning as well as lack of student confidence to express their views are the major factors affecting the practice of cooperative learning methods.

By supporting this, Muhammed (2014) also acknowledged that student motivation to work in groups; poor language ability and dominance of some students during group work were major problems hindering the practice of cooperative learning methods.

Regarding the above ideas of the interviewee, participant members state their views as follows.

Moreover, the result of an interview held with five of the senior teachers indicated “some students are careless, they do not take responsibility, and they need to gain benefits being on the shoulders of others.”

Concerning item 9 and 10, the mean scores teachers (M=3.42, SD=0.99) and (M=3.40, SD= 1.0) respectively, fall under agreement with the idea that poor educational background of students and teachers inability to provide clear procedures on how to perform the activity. This indicates teacher related factors such as their inability to share responsibility for each group members, lack of skill to manage activities during cooperative learning and inclination of interest towards lecturing method are highly affecting the cooperative learning also shows, teachers’ inability to provide timely feedbacks and their failure to reorganize group arrangement and poor educational background of students are highly affecting the cooperative learning. According to Wudu (2009), lack of teachers’ commitment was a major problem in using cooperative learning.

Table 6: Correlation between demographic characteristics and teachers perception

S.	Demographic characteristics Factors	1	2	3	4	5	6
1	Experience	1	0.943**	0.962**	0.95**	0.901**	0.976**
2	Teachers age	0.943**	1				
3	Teacher Education	0.962**		1			
4	Qualification	0.95**			1		
5	Teachers Gender	0.901**				1	
6	Perceived effect of cooperative learning	0.976**					1

**Correlation is significant at 0.01 levels (2-tailed)

As shown in above Table 6, correlation coefficient between demographic characteristics and teacher perception on cooperative learning experience and perceived effect of cooperative learning (r = 0.976) was the highest among all the demographic characteristics variables and it is significant at 0.01 (2-tailed).

Teacher level of education (r=0.962) has the second highest correlation coefficient among the demographic characteristics variables and significant at 0.00(2-tailed) under this sub title the items presented to the respondents to indicate their level of agreement toward teachers' level of education was positively correlated with effect of cooperative learning on student performances.

Teacher qualification (r=0.95) under this subtitle, the items presented for the respondents were; making cooperative learning on student results. The result shows an excellent correlation with the teacher's perception on cooperative learning.

Teachers age (r=0.943); under this subtitle, the items presented for the respondents were; teachers age are somewhat correlation with teacher’s perception on cooperative learning and Teachers Gender (r= 0.901) under this description the items presented for the respondents were teachers gender is highly correlated with perception towards effect of cooperative learning on students academic performance

4.4. Comparison of teacher’s perceptions across departments

No	Items	Group	Mean	STD	Mean Rank	Z- score	Sig.
1	There is a perception difference between teachers and teacher toward CL because of their different department	N/Sc	3.8	1.25	71.1	-0.1	0.92
		S/Sc	3.9	1.35	71.7		
2		N/Sc	3.76	1.18	70.4	-0.28	0.78

	Cooperative learning make significant change on student academic achievement for all department education	S/Sc	3.71	1.07	72.1		
3	The department head are evaluated and give feedback on practices of cooperative learning continuously	N/Sc	2.8	1.21	70.9	-0.15	0.88
		S/Sc	2.75	1.43	71.8		
4	The students are developing ability to improve their achievement because of cooperative learning is comfortable for all subject	N/Sc	3.31	1.07	68.3	-0.82	0.41
		S/Sc	3.29	1.33	73.3		
5	Peer interaction helps students to obtain a deeper understanding of the curriculum material	N/Sc	3.1	1.39	71.9	-0.16	0.87
		S/Sc	3.00	1.41	70.9		
6	Engaging students in group forms interfere and decrease students' academic progress	N/Sc	2.62	1.11	71.5	-0.23	0.79
		S/Sc	2.71	1.09	71.3		

As displayed on table 7 of item 1, respondents were asked whether the perception difference between teachers and teachers toward cooperative learning because of their different department or not. Accordingly, N/Sc teachers and S/Sc teachers agreed that the (M=3.8, STD=1.25) and (M=3.9, STD=1.35) responded respectively that there is a perception difference between teachers and teachers toward cooperative learning because of their different departments. In connection with this, the difference of the mean rank between N/Sc teachers and S/Sc teachers (Mean rank=71.1 & 71.7 respectively) is too small. Also, from Mann-Whitney Test at 0.05 significance level the computed significance value 0.92 showed that, there is no statistically significant difference between the two respondent groups. This means there is a difference in attitudes between teachers and teachers toward cooperative learning because of their different departments in their schools. Therefore, from the result of the responses it is recognized that there is a perception difference between teachers and teachers toward cooperative learning because of their different departments in the sample secondary schools.

According to item 2 of above table 7 of the respondents were asked to rate Cooperative learning to make significant changes on student academic achievement for all department education. Consequently, the mean scores result of N/Sc teachers and S/Sc teachers respondents were (M=3.76, STD=1.18) and (M=3.71, STD=1.07) respectively agreed on the item. In line to this the difference of the mean rank between N/Sc teachers and S/Sc teachers Mean rank=70.4, 72.1 respectively are small. Additionally, from Mann-Whitney Test at significance level of 0.05 the computed significance value 0.78 showed that, there is no statistically significant difference between the groups. This means that there is no evidence to identify the students that there is a difference in. From the result of the response it is concluded that Cooperative learning practice makes a significant change on academic achievement of the students of sample secondary schools.

According to item 3 of table 7, the respondents were asked to rate whether the department heads are evaluated and give feedback on practices of cooperative learning continuously or not. Consequently, N/Sc teachers and S/Sc teachers disagreed with the (M=2.8, STD=1.21) and (M= 2.75, STD=1.43) respectively, on the issue that department heads are evaluated and give feedback on practices of cooperative learning continuously. In connection with this, the difference of the mean rank between academic staff and administrative staff (Mean rank=70.9, 71.8 respectively) is small. Also, from Mann-Whitney Test (at significance level of 0.05) the computed significance value 0.88 showed that, there is no statistically significant difference between the two groups. This result revealed that there is no statistically significant difference between the two respondent groups. From the above results one can understand that department heads are evaluated and give feedback on practices of cooperative learning that are not continuously done.

Regarding item 4 of the above table, 7 of the respondents were asked whether the students are developing the ability to improve their achievement because cooperative learning is comfortable for all subjects. Consequently, N/Sc teachers and S/Sc teachers were undecided with the (M=3.31, STD=1.07) and (M= 3.29, STD=1.33) respectively, on the issue that the students are developing ability to improve their achievement because of cooperative learning is comfortable for all subject. In connection with this, the difference of the mean rank between Academic Staff and administrative staff (Mean rank=68.3, 73.3 respectively) is small. Also, from Mann-Whitney Test (at significance level of 0.05) the computed significance value 0.41 showed that, there is no statistically significant difference between the two groups. This result revealed that there is no statistically significant difference between the two respondent groups.

Therefore, from the results of the responses of the respondents, it is concluded that students are developing the ability to improve their achievement because cooperative learning practices in sample secondary schools are not active and students' ability varies subject wise.

Regarding the above ideas of the interviewee, participant members state their views as follows.

Five secondary school senior teachers explained that, in my school there is a practice of cooperative learning. The school prepared the plan to implement cooperative learning practices. Students are arranged in a group to learn in the class. However, the practice of cooperative learning is not active because only few teachers and few leaders are participating in cooperative learning practice continuously. In addition, the method of monitoring and evaluating by school leaders is not similar from school to school. School leaders, especially principals and vice principals are mostly focused on administrative activities rather than giving more attention for instructional supervision.

Beach and Reinhartz (2000) pointed out that instructional supervision is a process that focuses on instruction and provides teachers with information about their teaching (practice cooperative learning) so as to develop instructional skill to improve student performance. For group processing to be effective, teachers should provide students with an organized format for discussion. The purpose of group processing is to clarify and improve the effectiveness of the members in contributing to the efforts to achieve the group's goals (Sheehy, 2004).

In general, in most schools, the student achievement plan is not prepared individually by the student. The lesson plan format prepared by school did not have the method that is used to teach students in the classroom cooperatively. This shows that the participation of school leaders and teachers is not active in sampled secondary schools. But only some teachers were trying to use cooperative learning in student activities of the lesson plan. So, it was concluded that the practice of cooperative learning was not actively practiced in sampled secondary schools of Guji Zone. The practice is discontinuous in most subjects in all sampled schools.

According to item 5 of table 7, the respondents were asked to rate whether peer interaction helps students to obtain a deeper understanding of the curriculum material or not. Thus N/Sc teachers respondents were undecided with mean value of (M=3.1, STD= 1.39) and S/Sc teachers undecided with mean value of (M=3.00, STD= 1.41) reported that peer interaction helps students to obtain deeper understanding of the curricular material. In connection with this, the difference of the mean rank between Academic Staff and administrative staff (Mean rank=71.9, 70.9 respectively) is small. Also, from Mann-Whitney Test (at significance level of 0.05) the computed significance value 0.87 showed that there is no statistically significant difference between the two groups. This result revealed that there is no statistically significant difference between the two respondent groups. From the above results one can understand that peer interaction helps students to obtain a deeper understanding of the curriculum materialize not continuously done.

As shown on the table 7 of item 6, respondents were asked whether engaging students in group forms interfere and decrease students' academic progress or not; thus, N/Sc teachers (M= 2.62, STD= 1.11) and (M=2.71, STD= 1.09) S/Sc teachers disagreed with the question. In connection with this, the difference of the mean rank between Academic Staff and administrative staff (Mean rank=71.3, 71.5 respectively) is small. Also, from Mann-Whitney Test (at significance level of 0.05) the computed significance value 0.79 showed that there is no statistically significant difference between the two groups. This result revealed that there is no statistically significant difference between the two respondent groups. From the above results one can understand that engaging students in group forms did not interfere and decrease students' academic progress.

5. Summary, conclusions and recommendations

This section deals with the major findings, conclusions and recommendations based on the results obtained from the data analyzed and interpreted in section four. The primary objective of this section is to summarize the overall findings and draw conclusions based on the finding and put the way forward based on the conclusion.

5.1. Summary

The main objective of this study was to investigate the teacher's perception towards the effect of cooperative learning on student's academic performance in Secondary Schools in Guji zone. More specifically the study had designed to answer the following research questions:

1. What was the perception of teachers towards the effect of cooperative learning on student's academic performance in secondary schools in Guji zone?
2. What were the factors associated with the teachers' perceptions towards the effect of cooperative learning?
3. Did the teacher's perceptions towards the effect of cooperative learning vary across departments?

In order to find out the answer for the above research questions, a mixed approach was employed along with explanatory sequential design. Data were collected from 200 teachers through questionnaires and interviews. Quantitative data were analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistics such as frequency, percentage, mean, standard deviation, and Mann-Whitney test. While descriptive statistics were used to describe the findings of the survey results, inferential statistics was employed to test differences among the two groups (Natural science, and Social science teachers). Based on the result of analysis, major findings were summarized as follows:

Regarding with perception of teachers towards effect cooperative learning on student's academic performance

- Teachers showed an awareness gap to practice cooperative learning actively in sample secondary schools.
- Teachers confirmed their trust on the value of cooperative learning to develop students' communication skills and make tasks more simple or easy to complete.
- Most of the teachers believe that cooperative learning was less advantageous for students' learning, and they have not been practicing it effectively.

In general, based on the data collected from the different sources via different instruments regarding teachers' perception towards cooperative learning, it is possible to say that teachers have positive perception on cooperative learning. Similar to this finding Berhanu (2000) found that though teachers did not effectively practice cooperative learning, they had a favorable perception towards cooperative learning. Accordingly, the interview result found from the above interviewees can be summarized that the status of the implementation of cooperative learning was low and the reason for this situation was lack of teachers' knowledge on cooperative learning rather than their attitudinal problems.

Regarding with factors associated to the teacher's perceptions towards effect of cooperative learning

- Unwillingness of teachers, poor group coordination, and large group size were highly associated with teachers' perception towards influence cooperative learning on students' academic performance.
- Training gaps and student's less interest to be involved in cooperative learning had also moderately affected teachers' perception towards influence cooperative learning on students' academic performance.
- Similarly, less attention of school principals to facilitate the implementation cooperative learning had also significant effect on teachers' perception towards the effect of the program
- Tendency of over dominance of some students over the others during group work moderately affected teacher views towards the effect of cooperative learning.

In general, lack of proper ability to share responsibility for each group members, lack of skill to manage activities during cooperative learning and inclination of interest towards lecturing method, poor interest of students, and lack of teachers' commitment were highly associated to the perception of teachers on the effect of the cooperative learning on students' academic performance.

Regarding with difference in teacher's perceptions across departments (field of study)

- There is a perception difference between teachers of different departments (Natural science and Social science teachers) concerning the effect of cooperative learning on students' academic performance in sample secondary schools, but no difference was statistically significant.
- Teachers do not believe that students ability could improve because of cooperative learning practices in sample secondary school

5.2. Conclusions

Based on the major findings of the study, the following conclusions were arrived at.

The perception of teachers towards the effect of cooperative learning on students' academic performance was not satisfactory or less than an expected level. This result indicates weak awareness among teachers concerning the importance of cooperative learning for students' academic performance. From this, it can be concluded that the awareness gap of teachers has limited the practice of cooperative learning in secondary schools of Guji Zone.

Teachers tend to negatively perceive the effect of cooperative learning for improving the students' academic achievement. As a result their practice of cooperative learning was not as effective. From this, it can be concluded that less participation of school leaders and teachers in the implementation process limited the effectiveness of cooperative learning in improving students' academic performance in secondary schools of Guji Zone.

Quantitative results indicate that almost all of the participants seem to have a clear view point about cooperative learning. However, the data collected through an interview from a senior teacher indicates that almost all participants did not know why and how to implement cooperative learning in classroom instructions. Thus, it can be concluded that teachers of the sample schools seem to have different understanding about cooperative learning.

Poor training, unwillingness of students and large group size were found to be highly associated with teachers' perception towards effective cooperative learning. If teachers did not get any training about cooperative learning, their knowledge and practice could be greatly affected. Besides, if classrooms are not supportive, it would be difficult for cooperative learning implementation. Therefore, it can be concluded that, both teachers and school related factors appeared to have association with teachers' perception towards cooperative learning.

There is a perception difference between teachers of different departments concerning the effect of cooperative learning. Natural science teachers tend to have more negative perception as compared to their counterpart social science teachers. So, it can be concluded that the advantages of cooperative learning have not been equally recognized by departments in secondary schools of Guji Zone.

5.3. Recommendations

On the bases of findings and conclusions drawn above, the following recommendations are forwarded.

1. School leaders should facilitate training, workshops and experience-sharing programs to raise awareness of teachers and students on the role of cooperative learning.
2. The cooperative effort of local stakeholders (schools, Woreda, college of teacher education, and university) should be in place for supporting teachers in smoothly running the program into actual practice.
3. School leaders, Woreda Education office and School SIP committees should work together to facilitate experience sharing programs within and across schools.
4. The school leaders should plan to minimize the resistance by motivating teachers through discussion, continuous support and advice.
5. Teachers should apply the principles of cooperative learning while organizing students into different teams like assigning responsibility for each group member, and timely reorganizing the already stabilized groups.
6. School principals should reduce the number of students per class by increasing the number of sections and fulfilling the necessary materials through communicating with the community as well as the concerned government stakeholders.
7. Perception of teachers towards the effect of cooperative learning may affect students' perception and quality of instruction as well. Therefore, Zonal and Woreda education offices should have adequate training time devoted to acquaint teachers with how and when to effectively implement cooperative learning in classroom instructions.

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